

TEACHING COMPETENCY OF MATHEMATICS LEARNING FACILITATOR AMIDST NEW NORMAL EDUCATION: A MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION ANALYSIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10804183>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the teaching competency of mathematics learning facilitators at Agusan National High School during the 2021-2022 school year. The study focused on five competencies: instructional, guidance, management, interpersonal, and leadership skills. The research design used was correlational and causal. The researcher employed various statistical techniques such as frequency analysis, mean calculation, and independent sample t-tests to analyse the data. These analyses were conducted to determine significant differences in teaching competency ratings between the facilitators and administrators. Correlational analysis was also used to explore the relationship between teaching competency and demographic characteristics of the participants. The study's findings indicated that instructional, guidance, and leadership skills did not significantly differ in teaching competency. However, there were significant differences in the ratings of management and interpersonal skills between the facilitators and administrators. The study further revealed that the IPCRF performance ratings were consistently associated with the facilitators' instructional, guidance, interpersonal, and leadership skills. Regression analysis showed that the IPCRF performance rating for the school year (2020-2021) played a critical role in predicting the teaching competency of mathematics learning facilitators. In conclusion, the study emphasized the significance of management and interpersonal skills in teaching competency. It suggested that the IPCRF performance rating system could be used as a tool to assess and predict the teaching competency of mathematics learning facilitators.

Keywords: *guidance skills, instructional skills, interpersonal skills, leadership skills, management skills, teaching competency*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a public health emergency that has disrupted the global education system. To mitigate the possible educational gap caused by the crisis, various learning modalities, such as modular learning, online learning, and blended learning, have been endorsed for the continuity of learners' education. It has prompted academics worldwide to reassess traditional face-to-face instruction and investigate online education as a potential option for filling the empty classroom while reducing the risk of infectious disease among learners, as noted by Kaur in 2020 (cited by Adnan & Anwar, 2020). However, the shift to remote learning has also presented significant challenges, particularly for teachers expected to perform optimally in a virtual teaching environment. Despite these difficulties, the new normal in education offers growth and development opportunities for those willing to embrace change.

The term "new normal" in education refers to changes in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. In the Philippines, the new normal in education has been characterized by a shift to remote learning and the adoption of flexible learning modalities. Based on the DepEd Order No. 18, 2020, the Department of Education (DepEd) has implemented a blended learning approach, which combines different modalities such as online learning, printed modules, and TV and radio-based instruction. This approach addresses the lack of internet access and digital devices in some areas of the country. DepEd has also provided teachers with training on using digital tools and platforms to facilitate online learning. Schools have implemented safety measures such as physical distancing, wearing of masks and face shields, and regular disinfection to ensure the safety of students and staff who attend face-to-face classes.

The flow of education in the new normal remains challenging for teachers. Despite the absence of physical encounters, teachers are caught up with additional workloads. Most teachers stay at home and work from home and find themselves with overwhelming work. They must attend webinars, prepare lessons, print lessons and modules, answer student queries via phone, text, and Facebook messenger, attend virtual meetings, and tend to personal responsibilities at home. Furthermore, there are additional challenges to delivering learning in the new normal setting. Slow internet connections, no internet availability, students in remote areas, and some parents who cannot receive and return modules on time due to personal reasons all contribute to the difficulty in delivering the learning modality. In the traditional face-to-face setting, elite teachers would have known how to handle these situations. However, predicting how to handle these situations has become problematic in the new normal setting.

The teaching competency of teachers plays an essential role in pedagogy. Education, as described by Green (2014), has the objectives of providing individuals with skills,

changing society, and enhancing equality. Effective teaching involves the use of good pedagogical techniques by teachers to encourage students' active participation in the learning process. The ability of teachers to manage the educational process by using teaching methods and resources is referred to as their pedagogical competency (Safin, Korchagin, Vildanov, & Abitov, 2020). To be successful, teachers must be knowledgeable about instructional methods and learning styles and must be capable of implementing effective teaching practices that enable students to acquire and apply knowledge. Darling-Hammond and Berry (2006) assert that students' acquisition of knowledge through teaching helps them develop into more knowledgeable individuals. Costa, Cardoso, Lima, Ferreira, and Abrantes (2015) highlight the importance of a teacher's pedagogical competency in terms of teaching techniques, instructional resource utilization, and learner assessment. Having pedagogical knowledge is crucial in the development of educational policies aimed at improving teaching and learning (Ellahi & Zaka, 2015).

Research Questions

The study aimed to evaluate the Teaching Competency of Senior High School and Junior High School Mathematics Learning Facilitators amidst this new normal education during the School Year 2021-2022. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the demographic profile characteristics of the participants in terms of:
 - a. educational attainment;
 - b. Length of service;
 - c. c.no. of seminars/training attended ;
 - d. d.IPCRFP-Performance Rating for SY 2020-2021; and,
 - e. e.type of learning modality?
2. What are the teaching competencies of Mathematics Learning Facilitators as rated by teachers and administrators with respect to:
 - a. instructional skills ;
 - b. Guidance skills;
 - c. Management skills ;
 - d. interpersonal skills; and,
 - e. leadership skills?
3. Is there a significant difference in the teaching competency as rated by administrators and teachers?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teaching competency of Mathematics learning facilitators and their demographic profile characteristics?
5. To what extent do the demographic profile characteristics singly or in combination significantly influence the teaching competence of Mathematics Learning Facilitators?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at Agusan National High School (ANHS) in the Division of Butuan City. The division was grouped into fifteen (15) districts, and ANHS belongs to Central Butuan District 1 (CBD1). At least 30 senior high schools are in the Division of Butuan City, where ANHS is the biggest in enrollees. The appropriate random sampling design used in this study is stratified random sampling because the population parameter of this study is the mathematics learning facilitators of Agusan NHS, including the school administrators. Through this, it ensures the population receives proper representation within the sample. To gather the data needed in this study, the researchers used Cochran's alpha formula to determine the sample size. Thus, all selected mathematics learning facilitators and administrators would be considered the final participants of this study.

The research instrument used in gathering the data was the survey questionnaire adopted from the study of Catolos (2019) entitled 'Teaching Performance of Selected Public Secondary School Teachers in Tanay, Rizal.' The questionnaire checklist was divided into two parts, but only Part II was used in Catolos's study. Part I described the participants' profile, including personal variables such as educational attainment, length of service, IPCRF-performance rating 2020-2021, number of seminars or pieces of training attended, and learning modality. On the other hand, Part II focused on a discussion about the main problem of the study, containing variables such as instructional, guidance, management, interpersonal, and leadership skills. These variables were considered because it was believed they had a direct bearing on the problem investigated. To quantify the subjects' responses, a Likert-type questionnaire checklist was prepared where respondents could freely choose their answers.

Before the actual survey, the researchers wrote a letter asking permission from the School Principal to conduct a study. Upon approval, the researcher retrieved the request letter. Agusan National High School Mathematics Learning Facilitators in Butuan City were selected for administration. In administering the questionnaire, the researcher used a Google Forms survey to gather the data needed for this study. The researchers used Google Forms as the medium in collecting data because it is widely used to create surveys easily and quickly since they allow you to plan events, ask questions to your employees or clients, and manage diverse types of information simply and efficiently, especially in this new normal. The researcher used the vacant time allotted to avoid distraction from their work. The participants were given enough time to answer the questions. After the data had been gathered, the researcher collected it to tally the scores and applied the statistical treatment.

After the data gathered were compiled, sorted out, organized, and tabulated, the data was subjected to statistical treatment to facilitate the presentation, analysis, and interpretation.

The following statistical tools or test procedures were utilized:

1. Frequency count and percentages were used to determine the demographic profile of the participants through tables and bar graphs.
2. Weighted Mean (Average) was used to determine the level of teaching competency of a mathematics learning facilitator as rated by teachers and administrators.
3. Independent Sample T-Test was used to compare the means of two independent groups to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the associated population means are significantly different. This study would be used to find the significant difference in teaching competency as rated by teachers and administrators.
4. Correlational Analysis was used to measure how strong a relationship is between the teaching competency of a mathematics learning facilitator and their demographic profile characteristics. Pearson's Correlation (also called Pearson's R) is a correlation coefficient commonly used in linear regression.

The study is descriptive in nature and focused on both junior high school and senior high school mathematics learning facilitators and administrators of Agusan National High School, located in the City of Butuan. The research sample comprised fifty-three (53) Mathematics Learning Facilitators, including administrators. The primary data gathering tool was a survey questionnaire to determine their teaching competency. This study evaluated Mathematics Learning Facilitators' teaching competency amidst the New Normal Education.

RESULTS

Table 1. *Percentage and Frequency distribution of participants*

Group	Subgroup	Frequency	Percent
Educational Attainment	Bachelors Degree	7	13.73
	MA/MS Degree	7	13.73
	With unis MA/MS	37	72.55
Length of Service	5 years and Below	21	41.18
	6-10 years	15	29.41
	11-15 years	7	13.73
	21 years and above	8	15.69
IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021)	Outstanding	29	56.86
	Very Satisfactory	21	41.18
	Satisfactory	1	1.96
No. of Seminars/ Trainings Attended	1 Training/seminar	8	15.69
	2 Training/seminar	2	3.92

	3-5		
	Training/seminar	27	52.94
	More than 5 trainings	14	27.45
Type of Learning Modality	Modular	35	68.63
	Online Modular	16	31.37

Table 2.1 *Computed Weighted Mean on the teaching competency in terms of Instructional skill*

Instructional Skills	Rated by Teacher		Rated by Administrator	
	Mean	Verbal Description	Mean	Verbal Description
consider students' strengths and weaknesses in class	4.51	Outstanding	4.35	Very Satisfactory
cover all lessons indicated in the curriculum	4.20	Very Satisfactory	4.33	Very Satisfactory
create an inviting atmosphere for students to participate	4.39	Very Satisfactory	4.39	Very Satisfactory
develop the different abilities of students	4.22	Very Satisfactory	4.29	Very Satisfactory
encourage student participation during discussion	4.57	Outstanding	4.41	Very Satisfactory
formulate innovative teaching approaches to make learning Interesting	4.45	Very Satisfactory	4.45	Very Satisfactory
makes sure that students gain mastery of the lesson	4.35	Very Satisfactory	4.16	Very Satisfactory
performs tasks aligned to the desired learning competencies	4.37	Very Satisfactory	4.25	Very Satisfactory
prepare lessons and grades on time	4.53	Outstanding	4.47	Very Satisfactory
show mastery of the subject matter	4.55	Outstanding	4.59	Outstanding
Average	4.41	Very Satisfactory	4.37	Very Satisfactory

1.00-1.49-Poor, 1.50-2.49-Fair, 2.50-3.49-Satisfactory, 3.50-4.49-Very Satisfactory, 4.50-5.00-Outstanding

Table 2.2 *Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Teaching Competency in terms of Guidance Skills*

Guidance Skills	Rated by Teacher	Rated by Administrator
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	Mean	Verbal Description	Mean	Verbal Description
captivate the mood of the students through motherly/ fatherly approach	4.35	Very Satisfactory	4.33	Very Satisfactory
challenge students to share with one another and make them feel at home	4.45	Very Satisfactory	4.33	Very Satisfactory
create a feeling of security between and among class members	4.47	Very Satisfactory	4.41	Very Satisfactory
develop sense of belongingness to members of the class	4.57	Outstanding	4.31	Very Satisfactory
discuss topics that promotes good behavior	4.65	Outstanding	4.53	Outstanding
give positive advice to students with problems	4.59	Outstanding	4.51	Outstanding
perform tasks not only as teacher but also as guidance counselor	4.41	Very Satisfactory	4.39	Very Satisfactory
prepare all students mood before starting the lesson	4.59	Outstanding	4.49	Very Satisfactory
promote harmony among students with different interest	4.57	Outstanding	4.43	Very Satisfactory
share personal experiences to make the students feel at ease	4.49	Very Satisfactory	4.49	Very Satisfactory
Average	4.51	Outstanding	4.42	Very Satisfactory

1.00-1.49-Poor, 1.50-2.49-Fair, 2.50-3.49-Satisfactory, 3.50-4.49-Very Satisfactory, 4.50-5.00-Outstanding

Table 2.3 *Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Teaching Competency in terms of Management skills.*

Management Skills	Rated by Teacher		Rated by Administrator	
	Mean	Verbal Description	Mean	Verbal Description
administer school policies consistent with its vision and mission	4.45	Very Satisfactory	4.37	Very Satisfactory
supervise student activities	4.45	Very Satisfactory	4.24	Very Satisfactory
consider classroom behavior as the basis of good performance	4.45	Very Satisfactory	4.25	Very Satisfactory
create a very quiet but performing classroom atmosphere	4.37	Very Satisfactory	4.18	Very Satisfactory
display authority in and out of the classroom	4.49	Very Satisfactory	4.33	Very Satisfactory
encourage students participation after his /her talk	4.53	Outstanding	4.37	Very Satisfactory

impose discipline during classroom discussion	4.59	Outstanding	4.49	Very Satisfactory
organize the classroom according to students activities	4.51	Outstanding	4.35	Very Satisfactory
plan class activities according to school polices	4.51	Outstanding	4.43	Very Satisfactory
produce positive achievement through strict compliance with policies	4.43	Very Satisfactory	4.41	Very Satisfactory
Average	4.48	Very Satisfactory	4.34	Very Satisfactory

1.00-1.49-Poor, 1.50-2.49-Fair, 2.50-3.49-Satisfactory, 3.50-4.49-Very Satisfactory, 4.50-5.00-Outstanding

Table 2.4 *Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Teaching Competency in terms of Interpersonal Skills*

Interpersonal Skills	Rated by Teacher		Rated by Administrator	
	Mean	Verbal Description	Mean	Verbal Description
adjust to varying personal attitudes in the school	4.49	Very Satisfactory	4.47	Very Satisfactory
communicate pleasantly with all sectors in the school	4.25	Very Satisfactory	4.08	Very Satisfactory
consider others' feelings when talking of his/her opinion	4.37	Very Satisfactory	4.20	Very Satisfactory
consider sharing of knowledge with co-workers important in teaching	4.49	Very Satisfactory	4.18	Very Satisfactory
display equal authority inside school premises	4.51	Outstanding	4.39	Very Satisfactory
encourage others' opinion during discussion	4.51	Outstanding	4.25	Very Satisfactory
give constructive criticisms when necessary	4.39	Very Satisfactory	4.18	Very Satisfactory
help create a very friendly environment in school	4.57	Outstanding	4.33	Very Satisfactory
interact with students in and out of the school	4.33	Very Satisfactory	4.25	Very Satisfactory
mingle with co-employees during free time	4.45	Very Satisfactory	4.33	Very Satisfactory
Average	4.44	Very Satisfactory	4.27	Very Satisfactory

1.00-1.49-Poor, 1.50-2.49-Fair, 2.50-3.49-Satisfactory, 3.50-4.49-Very Satisfactory, 4.50-5.00-Outstanding

Table 2.5 Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Teaching Competency in terms of Leadership skills

Leadership Skills	Rated by Teacher		Rated by Administrator	
	Mean	Verbal Description	Mean	Verbal Description
ask suggestions from peers when doing group activities	4.60	Outstanding	4.76	Outstanding
consider new policies challenging	4.43	Very Satisfactory	4.41	Very Satisfactory
cooperate with superiors and peers	4.53	Outstanding	4.47	Outstanding
demonstrate creativity when doing assigned tasks	4.39	Very Satisfactory	4.25	Very Satisfactory
Always display positive attitude	4.71	Outstanding	4.67	Outstanding
exhibit professionalism in dealing with others	4.55	Outstanding	4.35	Very Satisfactory
perform assigned tasks by own initiative	4.49	Very Satisfactory	4.41	Very Satisfactory
perform tasks to the maximum standards	4.53	Outstanding	4.43	Very Satisfactory
respect others' opinion during brainstorming	4.63	Outstanding	4.51	Outstanding
show active participation in group work	4.61	Outstanding	4.49	Very Satisfactory
Average	4.55	Outstanding	4.48	Very Satisfactory

1.00-1.49-Poor, 1.50-2.49-Fair, 2.50-3.49-Satisfactory, 3.50-4.49-Very Satisfactory, 4.50-5.00-Outstanding

Table 3. Significance of the teaching competency as rated by administrators and learning facilitators

Teaching Competency	Rater	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value*	Remarks
Instructional	Learning Facilitator	4.41	0.48	0.856	Not Significant
	Administrator	4.37	0.51		
Guidance	Learning Facilitator	4.51	0.54	0.172	Not Significant
	Administrator	4.42	0.48		
Management	Learning Facilitator	4.48	0.48	0.047	Significant
	Administrator	4.34	0.37		
Interpersonal	Learning Facilitator	4.44	0.55	0.029	Significant

Leadership	Administrator	4.27	0.41	0.455	Not Significant
	Learning Facilitator	4.55	0.48		
	Administrator	4.48	0.45		

Table 4. Relationship between teaching competency and profile of mathematics learning facilitator.

Teaching competency	Profile	Spearman's rho	p-value	Remark
Instructional	Length of Service	-0.049	0.735	Not Significant
	IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021)	-0.474	0.000	Significant
	No. of Seminars/ Trainings Attended	0.483	0.000	Significant
	Type of Learning Modality	0.163	0.254	Not Significant
	Educational Attainment	-0.206	0.148	Not Significant
Guidance	Length of Service	0.191	0.179	Not Significant
	IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021)	-0.286	0.042	Significant
	No. of Seminars/ Trainings Attended	0.343	0.014	Significant
	Type of Learning Modality	-0.044	0.759	Not Significant
	Educational Attainment	-0.148	0.300	Not Significant
Management	Length of Service	0.062	0.668	Not Significant
	IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021)	-0.222	0.118	Not Significant
	No. of Seminars/ Trainings Attended	0.214	0.131	Not Significant
	Type of Learning Modality	-0.102	0.477	Not Significant
	Educational Attainment	-0.264	0.062	Significant
Interpersonal	Length of Service	0.042	0.771	Not Significant
	IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021)	-0.295	0.036	Significant
	No. of Seminars/ Trainings Attended	0.135	0.344	Not Significant
	Type of Learning Modality	-0.235	0.097	Significant
	Educational Attainment	-0.394	0.004	Significant
Leadership	Length of Service	0.036	0.799	Not Significant
	IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021)	-0.314	0.025	Significant
	No. of Seminars/ Trainings Attended (0.204	0.152	Not Significant

Type of Learning Modality	-0.101	0.479	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	-0.317	0.023	Significant

Table 5.1 Regression Analysis summary for teaching competence of mathematics learning facilitator towards profile

Variable	β Coefficients	Standard Error	t –Statistic	P-value	Remark
Intercept	4.366	0.237	18.422	0.000	Significant
IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021)	-0.374	0.102	-3.667	0.000	Significant
No. of Seminars/ Trainings Attended	0.202	0.056	3.576	0.000	Significant

Note: $R^2 = 0.373$ ($Df = 2, F = 14.307, p < 0.001$), dependent variable= Instructional Skills

Table 5.2. Regression Analysis summary for teaching competence of mathematics learning facilitator towards profile

Variable	β Coefficients	Standard Error	t –Statistic	P-value	Remark
Intercept	4.363	0.305	14.314	0.000	Significant
IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021)	-0.236	0.131	-1.796	0.079	Significant
No. of Seminars/ Trainings Attended	0.169	0.073	2.32	0.025	Significant

Note: $R^2 = 0.163$ ($Df = 2, F = 4.682, p < 0.014$), dependent variable=Guidance Skills

Table 5.3. Regression Analysis summary for teaching competence of mathematics learning facilitator towards profile

Variable	β Coefficients	Standard Error	t –Statistic	P-value	Remark
Intercept	5.87	0.485	12.111	0.000	Significant

IPCRF					
Performance Rating (2020-2021)	-0.251	0.144	-1.741	0.088	Significant
Educational Attainment	-0.183	0.105	-1.756	0.086	Significant
Type of Learning Modality	-0.256	0.161	-1.594	0.118	Not significant

Note: $R^2 = 0.187$ ($Df = 3, F = 3.593, p < 0.020$), dependent variable=Interpersonal Skills

Table 5.4. Regression Analysis summary for teaching competence of mathematics learning facilitator towards profile

Variable	β Coefficients	Standard Error	t –Statistic	P-value	Remark
Intercept	5.242	0.265	19.804	0.000	Significant
IPCRF					
Performance Rating (2020-2021)	-0.23	0.124	-1.853	0.070	Significant
Educational Attainment	-0.14	0.093	-1.512	0.137	Not Significant

Note: $R^2 = 0.141$ ($Df = 2, F = 3.946, p < 0.026$), dependent variable=Leadership Skills

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows participants of this study work in the Department of Education Butuan City Division and are assigned to Agusan National High School, whose mathematics facilitators include administrators. The participants of this study are (33) JHS teachers, (18) SHS teachers and (2) school administrators. Most participants have an educational attainment of 72% with MA/MS units, 14% have a bachelor's degree, and 14% have a master's degree. Among the participants, 21 have been teaching for five years and below, 15 have served 6-10 years, seven facilitators have rendered 11-15 years, and eight have rendered 21 years and above. Regarding performance rating, 57% have an outstanding IPCRF rating, 2% received a satisfactory rating, and 41% received a "very satisfactory" evaluation. Regarding attendance to seminars/training, 27 participants have attended 3-5 sessions, 14 have heard more than five sessions, and only two have attended two sessions. Furthermore, 69% of the mathematics learning facilitators handle modular distance learning simultaneously, while 31% manage both online and modular distance learning.

Table 2 1 shows the results of the teaching competency in terms of instructional skills as rated by teachers and administrators. Both teachers and administrators assessed "Very Satisfactory" on instructional skills with an overall weighted mean of 4.41 and 4.37, respectively. As rated by teachers, there are three (3) indicators where they possess an outstanding rating as follows: consider students' strengths and weaknesses in class; prepare lessons and grades on time; while teachers and administrators have the same exceptional rating on "showing mastery of the subject matter."

Moreover, the findings reveal that as rated by teachers and administrators, they possess the necessary competencies as a teacher. This implies that the participants are doing their best to deliver quality instruction to their students. This aligns with Lapuz's (2010) assertions that great teachers must comprehend the material they teach and know how to convey it to students.

Table 2.2 shows the results on the level of teaching competency regarding guidance skills as rated by teachers and administrators. The teacher's overall weighted mean is 4.51, showing an outstanding rating, while the administrator's overall weighted mean is 4.42, indicating a very satisfactory rating. As rated by the teacher, five (5) indicators that possess outstanding results as follows: develop a sense of belongingness among members of the class; prepare all students' moods before starting the lesson; promote harmony among students with different interests; while teachers and administrators have the same outstanding rating on discussing topics that promote good behavior; and give positive advice to students with problems.

Furthermore, the outcomes also show that the teachers effectively guide their students. The study by Glewwe (2003) that the teachers should be able to change based on the needs and skills of students finds congruence in the outcome, which suggests that teachers also work as guidance counselors to their students to ensure their good behavior inside and outside of the classroom.

Table 2.3 shows the results on the level of teaching competency in terms of management skills as rated by teachers and administrators. Both teachers and administrators assessed "Very Satisfactory" on management skills with an overall weighted mean of 4.48 and 4.34, respectively. As rated by the teacher, four (4) indicators have outstanding results: encourage students' participation after their talk, impose discipline during class discussion, organize the classroom according to students' activities, and plan class activities according to school class policies. As rated by the administrators, all indicators have a verbal description of "Very Satisfactory", the highest weighted mean obtained of 4.49, indicating that the learning facilitators impose discipline during classroom discussion.

Additionally, the findings reveal that teachers have very satisfactory performance in terms of their management skills and teaching competency. It could mean that teachers employ varied classroom management strategies for an effective teaching-learning process. A good teacher pushes their students, according to Lardizabal (2003). The professors that many students find to be the most challenging are frequently the ones who are the most effective.

Table 2.4 shows the results on the level of teaching competency in terms of interpersonal skills as rated by teachers and administrators. Both teachers and administrators assessed "Very Satisfactory" on interpersonal skills with an overall weighted mean of 4.44 and 4.27, respectively. As rated by the teacher, three (3) indicators have outstanding results, as follows: display equal authority inside the school premises, encourage others' opinions during discussions and help create a very friendly environment in school. As rated by the administrators, all indicators have a verbal description of "Very Satisfactory", the highest weighted mean obtained of 4.47, indicating that the learning facilitators can adjust to varying personal attitudes in the school.

This suggests that teachers get along well with everyone at the school. Teachers are also capable of adapting to their chosen careers. This aligns with Ladd's (2006) assertion that a teacher's love and passion for their subject matter is the single most critical attribute they should possess. The finest instructors make an extra effort to establish connections with each pupil.

Table 2.5 shows the results on the level of teaching competency in terms of leadership skills as rated by teachers and administrators. The teacher's overall weighted mean is 4.55, indicating an outstanding rating, while the administrator's overall weighted mean is 4.48, showing a very satisfactory rating. As rated by the teacher, seven (7) indicators have outstanding results, as follows: exhibit professionalism, perform tasks to the maximum standards, show active participation in group work while teachers and administrators have the same exceptional rating as mentioned: ask suggestions from peers when doing group activities, cooperate with superiors and peers, always display a positive attitude and respect others opinion during brainstorming.

According to research, teachers make strong leaders and exemplary followers of their superiors. This agrees with Haslett's (2003) results that effective leadership is one factor in teacher effectiveness.

As reflected in **Table 3**, concerning the teaching competencies in Management and Interpersonal skills as rated by learning facilitators and administrators, the computed p values obtained probability values not exceeding 0.05. This rejects the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the teaching competency rated by facilitators and administrators regarding management and interpersonal skills. On the other hand, in terms of Instructional, Guidance, and Leadership Skills, the null hypothesis is accepted since the computed p -values in all aspects obtained p -values exceeding 0.05. This means that the rater agreed with this enumerated teaching competency which is not significant.

As reflected in **Table 4**, concerning instructional and guidance skills in terms of IPCRF Performance rating (2020-2021), the number of seminars and training attended computed p values obtained probability values not exceeding 0.10. This means that the IPCRF performance rating (2020-2021) and seminars and training attended are significant to their instructional and guidance skills. On the other hand, for the length of service, learning modality, and educational attainment, the computed p -values obtained exceeded 0.10. This implies that it is insignificant to their instructional and guidance skills.

Concerning instructional and guidance skills in terms of IPCRF Performance rating (2020-2021), the number of seminars and training attended computed p values obtained probability values not exceeding 0.10. This means that the IPCRF performance rating (2020-2021) and seminars and training attended are significant to their instructional and guidance skills. On the other hand, for the length of service, learning modality, and educational attainment, the computed p -values obtained exceeded 0.10. This implies that it is insignificant to their instructional and guidance skills.

Regarding management skills in terms of educational attainment, the computed p -values obtained probability values not exceeding 0.10. This means that educational attainment is significant to their management skills. On the other hand, IPCRF performance rating, the length of service, learning modality, and the number of seminars and training attended, the computed p values obtained probability values exceeding 0.10. This implies that it is insignificant to their management skills. A good teacher must know the students' psychological requirements, adaptive actions, and limitations (Dunhill, 2000). The guiding principle is that well-run classrooms facilitate efficient teaching and learning. The learners' incapacity frequently causes poor academic performance to control the school environment and behavior (Oliver et al., 2007).

Concerning interpersonal and leadership skills in terms of IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) and educational attainment, the computed p -values obtained probability values not exceeding 0.10. This means that the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) and seminars and training attended are significant to their interpersonal and leadership skills. However, regarding the type of learning modality, their interpersonal

skills are significant since the p -value does not exceed 0.10. On the other hand, the length of service and the number of seminars and training attended, the computed p -values obtained exceeded 0.10. This implies that it is not significant to their interpersonal and leadership skills. Moreover, the type of learning modality shows non-significant leadership skills. According to Kumari and Dubey (2020), a teacher is responsible for fostering a positive learning environment in the classroom.

The analysis revealed in **table 5.1** that the IPCRF Performance rating (2020-2021) has a significant negative relationship with ($\beta = -0.374, p = 0.000$) and no. of seminars and training attended has a significant positive relationship ($\beta = 0.202, p = 0.000$). IPCRF Performance rating (2020-2021) and the number of seminars and training attended accounts for 37.3% of the variance in Instructional skills ($Df = 2, F = 14.307, p < 0.001$). This displays that as teaching competency in instructional skills increases, the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) decreases. On the other hand, the more seminars and training a participant attends, the higher their teaching competency is. It suggests that the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) and the number of seminars and training attended play a pivotal role in predicting the teaching competency of mathematics learning facilitators regarding instructional skills.

The analysis revealed in **table 5.2** that the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) has a significant negative relationship with ($\beta = -0.236, p = 0.079$), and the number of seminars and training attended has a significant positive relationship ($\beta = 0.169, p = 0.025$). IPCRF Performance rating (2020-2021) and the number of seminars and training attended account for 16.3% of the variance in guidance skills ($Df = 2, F = 4.682, p < 0.014$). This displays that as teaching competency in guidance skills increases, the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) decreases. On the other hand, the more seminars and training a participant attends, the higher their teaching competency is. It suggests that the IPCRF Performance rating (2020-2021) and the no. of seminars and training attended play a pivotal role in predicting the teaching competency of Mathematics Learning Facilitators regarding Guidance Skills.

The analysis revealed in **table 5.3** that the IPCRF Performance rating (2020-2021) and Educational attainment has a significant negative relationship with ($\beta = -0.251, p = 0.088$; ($\beta = -0.183, p = 0.086$) *respectively*. IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021), educational attainment, and learning modality account for 18.7% of the variance in interpersonal skills ($Df = 3, F = 3.593, p < 0.020$). Moreover, the results also show that type of learning modality does not impact the teaching competency with ($\beta = -0.256, p = 0.118$). This shows that as teaching interpersonal skills competency increases, the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) decreases. On the other hand, the lower their educational attainment or equivalent to a bachelor's degree, the higher their teaching competency is. It suggests that the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) and educational attainment play a pivotal role in predicting the teaching competency of mathematics learning facilitators regarding Interpersonal Skills.

The analysis revealed in **table 5.4** that the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) has a significant negative relationship with ($\beta = -0.23, p = 0.070$) *respectively*.

IPCRF Performance rating (2020-2021) and educational attainment account for 14.1% of the variance in leadership skills ($Df = 2, F = 3.946, p < 0.026$). Moreover, the results also show that educational attainment does not impact teaching competency with ($\beta = -0.14, p = 0.093$). This displays that as teaching competency in leadership skills increases, the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) decreases. It suggests that the IPCRF Performance Rating (2020-2021) plays a pivotal role in predicting the teaching competency of Mathematics Learning Facilitators regarding Leadership Skills.

Conclusions

Based on the study, the researcher concluded that the teaching competency of the mathematics learning facilitators at Agusan National High School at all levels has a very satisfactory performance as rated by school administrators. However, as rated by the learning facilitator, only guidance and leadership skills have outstanding teaching competencies. These teaching competencies involve instructional, guidance, management, interpersonal, and leadership. This implies that the teacher's knowledge, skills, and ability are employed to develop meaningful pedagogic experiences for students.

In this case that the level of instructional, guidance, and leadership skills of the mathematics learning facilitators show no significant difference in their teaching competency as rated by the administrator and facilitator. Thus, only management and interpersonal skills appear to be significant. The study also concluded that the instructional and guidance skills of mathematics learning facilitators are associated with their IPCRF performance rating and the number of seminars and training attended. With regards to management skills, they are associated with their educational attainment. With regards to interpersonal skills, they are associated with their IPCRF performance rating, type of learning modality, and educational attainment. With regards to leadership skills, they are associated with their IPCRF performance rating and educational attainment.

Furthermore, the facilitator IPCRF Performance rating for SY 2020-2021 is pivotal in predicting teaching competency in all skills.

Recommendations

The researcher offered the following recommendations based on the salient findings obtained in the study:

1. The facilitators are encouraged to personally upgrade their teaching competency by attending learning and development opportunities, enrolling in graduate studies (Master's and Doctorate degrees) for personal and professional growth and development, and attending short courses.
2. School administrators are encouraged to conduct regular teachers' assessments and training needs evaluations to identify the needs of teachers in terms of their profession. Teacher education programs may be given much attention, especially

in lesson content, quality of students being admitted, and quality teachers being created.

3. Education Program Supervisors may provide facilitators with the necessary professional growth in teaching competency through seminars, training, and sessions that promote professional development to improve student performance. Seminars, training, and workshops may focus on innovative techniques for proper coaching and mentoring teachers.
 4. The school management is encouraged to organize in-house teacher capability training to enrich motivational techniques in all aspects of teaching competency
 5. The Department of Education may use this study to monitor a learning facilitator's teaching competency. Implementing the proposed plan of action should be encouraged by school administrators and embraced by public education continuously.
 6. Future researchers may use this study as a starting point to investigate additional factors that might be considered in related investigations.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The following are necessary to guarantee that research is carried out ethically and honestly.

Informed consent. In order to conduct a study, the head of the school will be written a letter by the researcher to gain permission. The participants will be informed particularly about all the aims and objectives of the research.

Privacy and Confidentiality. The participants are given orientation before answering the survey questionnaire in pursuance of RA 10173 or Data Privacy Act of 2012, all personal and/or sensitive information collected and disclosed by this survey shall be used solely for purposes of the study.

Conflict of Interest. The researchers are disclosing any financial or personal conflicts of interest that could potentially bias the results or their interpretation.

Fairness and Equity. Researchers make sure that everyone is treated equally, respectfully, and without prejudice based on factors like ethnicity, gender, or socioeconomic position.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to extend their sincere thanks to Agusan National High School, DepEd Butuan City Division, Butuan City, Philippines for allowing them to conduct the study.

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APA citation:

Pasok, N. C. B., & Lingo, J. T. (2024). TEACHING COMPETENCY OF MATHEMATICS LEARNING FACILITATOR AMIDST NEW NORMAL EDUCATION: A MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION ANALYSIS. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(3), 254–272. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10804183>

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